

IMPACT OF SALES PROMOTIONAL TOOLS ON PURCHASE INTENTION**AUTHORS****Muhammad Rizwan¹, Qasim irshad (Corresponding Author)², Kashif Ali³,****Muhammad Nadir⁴, Muhammad Ejaz⁵,**

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Abstract: Sales promotion is important area for researching because it provides information and knowledge that which promotional technique is performing in a better way and how can any marketer compete and gain competitive advantage by using the promotional tools in the market and for the enhancement of sale. The main aim of the research was checking the weight of sales promotion on purchase intention of the students of university. Exclusively, we choose Islamia University of Bahawalpur (IUB) as study location. We have selected 150 respondents for sampling. We have gathered the data through questionnaires that we administered in university. The result shows that attitude towards price discount and free sample have considerable encouraging affiliation amid ($\beta = 0.239$) and ($p < 0.01$), ($\beta = 0.193$) and ($p < 0.05$) respectively. Regression results institute that price discount and free sample explained 25% and 16% variance inside purchase intention respectively. The findings of our study can become helpful for the marketers to recognize the types of promotions that considerably manipulate purchase intention of the respondents. Thus, this study can help the marketers in making plans for becoming supplementary competitive and get distinctive reward.

Keywords: Purchase Intention, Price Discount, Free Sample, In-store Display, University students

1. Introduction

Sales promotion based on those promotional tricks, which are other than advertisement, selling personally, and exposure. For example, an airline company makes offers discount cards to its passengers, which become mean to purchase any thing at greatly reduced prices from an eminent company. Promotion is a broader scope term that includes sales promotion as well as the other promotional tricks. There are different ways of sales promotion. Mostly these ways of promotion used: coupons, drawings, games, contests, discounts, buy one get one free,

Demonstrations, premiums, samples, money refund offers, and trading stamps. We are touching some of ways for our study

Purposes. Now a day, every business needed to have some brilliant marketing planning to get better the efficiency and effectiveness of their activities and operations. De Chernatony and McDonald, 2003 describes that to introduce any new brand or product, sales promotional tools are dominant resources. Whereas in the past the only medium, advertisement was used for introducing and promoting any product. Advertising media was a more successful way to

market a business and it casted positive impact on sales of more products and brands. However, these days, promotion mean is casting attractive impact on sales and goodwill rising (Peattie and Peattie 1995, Shultz 1987, Bayer and Kean, 1986 ;). Due to expensive media of publicity and advertisement, less reliable mean of promoting brands and products, companies and industries switch to sales promotional tools (Dickson and Sawyer, 1990; Quelch, 1983). Neslin and Blattberg 1990, says that firms' customer purchase intention influenced by sales promotion. Different types of selling incentives and techniques are included in sale promotion in order to create a short-term as well as long-term sales effect.

- 1) Consumers' Promotion
- 2) Trading Promotion
- 3) Retailers' Promotion

These are the categories of selling techniques in case of sales promotion. In case of consumers' promotion the marketer can use samples, coupons, discounts, price packs, refunds, bonus, contests and special events to made the customer to make a purchase. Advertising allowances, Case allowances, trade coupons, display allowances, contests and financing incentives designed by producers to inspire marketing mediators in trade promotion. In retailer promotions price cuts/deal, retailers to catch the attention of shoppers and in-store purchasing initiate display, feature advertisement, free goods and services, retailer coupons and contest or premium. Wathieu and Murre, 2007 that when any consumer makes some purchases, he makes these purchases usually with very little cognitive activity, narrate it. In these situations, it is very tough to inspire behavior, as switching any brand or enhances the quantity of units bought. It is the return of the promotion that they can inspire customers to have interest, appraise product, and increase buying possibility on the other hand customers not having it. For that reason market managers and retailers operate many types of promotional tools and strategies for understanding the costumers preferences and boost up their sales. The observations of Moon, 2003 tell us that in Malaysia,

as a shopping intention a plan made to go round the international summary of the country. An event take place in Malaysia for the purpose of sales promotion in which a result came across that the harsh promotion type is discount. This event occurs three times in a year and identify as Malaysia Mega Sales Carnival (MAMSC), which launches in March, August and December every year (Faiz, 2009). The purpose of the event (MAMSC) is to attract more and more consumers to expend and consume money to purchases the goods they want to have through this event. They also believe that through the sales promotion event, charges of all goods and brands are less than customary. Gilbert and Jackaria 2002, a broad range of short-term planned promotion activities designed for creating a most wanted reply from consumers in sales promotion. The growth of the research in this field is extraordinary due to rising concentration in the utilization of sales promotional tools as a marketing strategy. Huge body of literature on customer intention towards sales promotions is available (Shoemaker and Bawa, 1987 and 1989; Gupta, 1988; Neslin and Blattberg, 1990; Srinivasan, 1996; Alden and Huff, 1998). The understanding and knowledge of marketing and promotional tools is indeed important for influencing the tools to try to win with competitors. With the knowledge of marketing tools, market managers and retailers could healthy plan the resources to attain the utmost return. This research want to inspect the preferences, choices of customers on different promotional tools, market managers and retailers will proficiently design promotion techniques and strategies. Therefore, they can build up the accurate and the most effectual promotional method to create a center of customers' attention. From the customer point of view, this research will expose the customer attitude toward sales promotional tools (Price discount and free sample) and as a result heave the intention of the customers affected by sales promotion. It provides improved information and understanding to customers where the purchase intention of them would make profile in a different way because of different kinds of promotional tools. Through it they can understand how the

retailer design different promotions to capture their attention to purchase. Price discount is deduction from the total price for the promotion of product. Same product is available at fewer prices in case of price discount and it is an independent variable, which has impact on purchase intention. In case of free sample promotional tool, free products and services given for promotion and development of the brand and it is an independent variable, which has impact on purchase intention. In-store Display In-store display tool used to attract the visitors and customers by seeing display of products in a good and attractive way and it is an independent variable, which has impact on purchase intention. Purchase intention is dependent variable, which depends upon different tools that are used by retailers and marketers. In this study, we are going to test the impact of promotions (Price discount, free samples and in-store display) on consumer purchase. This understanding and knowledge is significant, particularly to market stakeholders in understanding the importance and usefulness of applying these promotional activities on customers.

Abbreviations-Attitude towards Price Discount (**ATPD**), Attitude towards Free Sample (**ATFS**), In-store Display (**ISD**), and Purchase Intention (**PIN**)

2. Literature and Hypotheses

2.1 Purchase intention:

PIN is a plan to purchase a particular good or service in the future.

The data on PIN used as an input to making strategic decisions related with both new and existing products and the marketing programs that support them. In case of any new product, purchase intention utilized in testing the concept, which provide help to the manager for the determination of concept qualities for development. In case of launching new products, PIN help the manager to come to a decision in which markets and to which customer segment the product should launch.

PINs used for existing product to make prediction for its prospect demand (Urban and Hauser, 1993; Morrison, 1979; Sewall, 1978; Urban and Silk, 1978; Juster, 1966 ;). The above-mentioned forecasts are used as very important and useful key inputs in making decisions about the production level should it be increase or decrease, should sale size be increase or decrease, should the prices of product be increase or decrease. PIN utilized for pretesting marketing and weighting up planned promotion in case of both existing and new product (Ehrenberg and Bird, 1966). Academic researchers, Schlosser, 2003 as substitute measures for purchase intention also widely use PINs. However, the correctness with which PINs expect succeeding sales can show a discrepancy largely.

Morwitz, Steckel, and Gupta discover in the research the elements which cast affect on the projecting truthfulness of PINs data. The outcomes supply managers the knowledge and information that provide help them to intend studies to exploit and increase the projecting strength of PINs, and help them to understand how much they should rely on intentions data when making strategic decisions on which their success depends.

2.2 Price discount:

Price discount is deduction from the total price for the promotion of product. Same product is available at fewer prices in case of price discount and it is an independent variable, which has impact on PIN.

In pricing literature, indoctrination means the slanted interpretation and explanation of aimed prices and price discounts (Olson and Jacoby 1977; Monroe 1984; Zeithaml 1984). About reference price, it means that it is a price, which a customer has in his mind of any product, against which he compare the price of current product. The concept of reference price that is reliable with adaptation-level theory (Helson 1964) and assimilation-contrast theory says that customers have inner perceived prices against which he compared current prices (Sherif 1963; Winer 1986; Dickson and Urbany 1991). The perceived discount (PD) is therefore the projected

savings from this inner perceived price (Mobley *et al.* 1988; Monroe 1977; Winer 1986).

Advertised Discount (defined in this study as the % cut regular price) by retailers' increases, consumers' perceptions of the discounts or savings that also increase their purchase intention. This is undoubtedly the fundamental basis for most promotional offerings, and it supported by numerous studies (Berkowitz and Walton 1980; Della Bitta, Monroe, and McGinnis 1981; Mobley *et al.* 1988). Is the PD less than the AD? Numerous studies addressed this question in relative to the issue raised by Federal Trade Commission cases dealing with the equality of reference price advertising by retailers. Critics of advertised reference price says that retailers typically increase these prices and distort the perceptions of consumer about the savings offered (Urbany, Weillbaker and Bearden, 1988; Heslop and Liefeld 1985 ;).

Do the discounts increase with the increase in the AD level? The answer of it is yes. Della Bitta *et al.* (1981) say that if the price reduces very much, consumers may know that the offer is not authentic. Fry and McDougall (1974) say that high offer savings results in few customers believing the reference price. Urbany *et al.* (1988) suggested that discounting might be a usual comeback of consumers, mostly advertisements makes savings overstated claims. The findings of Della Bitta and Monroe's (1980) suggest that the perceptions of the customers' about savings do not significantly be at variance between 30 percent and 50 percent discount levels, hence in a approximately way signifying a bigger discounting of claimed savings at 50 percent than at 30 percent.

Berkowitz and Walton, 1980 depict that link between ADs and PDs, It discussed most probably; retailers' chief aim in offering price promotions is to capture consumers' purchase intention. There are many important issues arise in light of this literature. A most important issue of researchers for customers and retailers is that how promotions have an effect on consumers' PINs. Discussion made on the link of price discount and advertised discount provide help to understand the matter, which is, advertised discount casts affect on price

discount, through the outcome, it casts affect on the intentions of customers in buying the products. An example tells that increment in advertised discount is expecting to add to the view of customers' about the discounts, which are in turn after those enhance the customers' intentions in buying any product, brand or service.

Fill (2002) say that discount is the simple procedure in which straight drop made in the purchase price with the offer clearly labeled on the package or spot of purchase display. Brandweek 1994 describes price promotion does influence new product testing. Consumer's response more favorably price-off promotions, reported by Percy *et al.* (2001). Ndubisi and Chiew (2005) say that price discount had strapping impact on product testing. According to Ehrenberg *et al.* (1994), the customer will move to a brand which offer price discount if he usually not purchase that product.

Price discount influences the consideration of customers to make any purchase, Pery *et al.* (2001). Chiew and Ndubisi (2005) say that, consumer PIN influenced greatly by PD. Observation tells that if any price discount offered on any product the customer purchase its extra quantity due to price benefit.

H 1: Attitude towards Price discount (ATPD) promotion has positive impact on consumer Purchase intention (PIN).

2.3 Free sample:

In case of Free Sample promotional tool, products and services given as free for promotion and development of the brand and it is an independent variable, which has impact on PIN. It is also a significant promotion means, which retailers and marketing manager use. In 1999, Kardes says that they usually launch the products as free sample to customers or trying the products, in spite of listen to concerning the goods. Along with framing promotion, price promotion is varied forms like coupon, discount, purchasing along gifts and rebates. Some kinds of promotion are monetary savings and some are non-monetary. Often used non-monetary promotion is free sample, which

offers product to customers as gift or free in spite of discounting.

In contrast, the discounting, non-price promotion like free sample gives small gains and support the quality awareness of product as compared the discounting (Diamond and Johnson, 1990; Chung and Darke, 2005). Discounting lessen the prices which paid by customers for products. However, in case of sampling promotions, promotion's worth might be equal to discounting; these do not sacrifice with the central purchasing of products. Therefore, it recognizes it like reward. With or without pre-purchasing objectives act in response in a different way for gaining or losing the awareness of promotion, which might act in response in a different way in case of price promotions, monetary and non-monetary.

A price discount was often selected even the discounts were fewer as compared to retailing worth of free products. We have discussed before that the customers, who are making plans for buying anything, spotlight further at pecuniary forfeit; they will good turn discounting by reducing losses as compared to sampling promotions gaining little. In addition, the customers, not making plans for buying further attractive for little gaining linked along sampling (Diamond and Abhijit, 1990).

Samples provide free of cost products to the customers for trying and testing features of products. In 2003, Shimp says, samples, which provided to customers as free have enormous contact on the PIN of customers.

H 2: Attitude towards Free Sample (FSL) promotion has positive impact on Purchase intention (PIN).

2.4 In-store display:

ISD tool, used to attract the visitors and customers by seeing display of products in a good and attractive way and it is an independent variable, which has impact on PIN. Pramataris 2001 say that ISD is the product attributing, physical appearance and display of product in the store. Percy et al. (2001) says that promotions in which products displayed could be an integer part of an incorporated marketing programmer. Attractive presented material leads to enhance the concentration, particularly for brands motivated by identification alertness. He also advised that display should be consistent with consumer promotion and advertising; it should appear and feel, so that it increases identification at the time of purchase. Chiew and Ndubisi (2005) say that for Malaysian consumers ISD to be a momentous aspect of product testing.

In today's competitive marketplace, businesses have intense on all aspects of their products from its production to its selling; among all other aspects, the store environment considered a vital one as the retail store is the point of purchase for the customer.

Yalcin & Kocamaz, 2003, Bitner, 1992 suggest that retailers have realized the impact of store atmosphere, which enhances the purchase experience and renders more customers that are contented. The customers pay supplementary concentration to three dimensions of store atmosphere, which are ambience, space and signs, symbols and artifacts.

H 3: In-store display (ISD) promotion has positive impact on consumer Purchase intention (PIN).

Figure 1: Research Model

3. Research Methodology

The nature of current research is descriptive. Descriptive research explained as describing something, some phenomenon or any particular situation. In 1994, Creswell told that descriptive researches are those researches, which describe the existing situation instead of interpreting and making judgments. Verification of the developed hypotheses that reflect the current situation is the main objective of the descriptive research. This

type of research provides information about the current scenario and focus on past or present for example, quality of life in a community or customer attitudes and towards sales promotional tools.

3.1. Sample/data

In order to collect the data for understanding the impact of sales promotional tools on purchase intention, a sample of 150 respondents will ask in a self-administered questionnaire. The population for the current research is users of grocery items in Pakistan.

The current study utilizes a non-probability sampling technique that is convenience sampling. Convenience

sampling is a sampling technique that obtains and collects the relevant information from the sample or the unit of the study that are conveniently available (Zikmund, 1997). We used convenience sampling normally for collecting a large number of completed surveys promptly and with economy.

It has ensured that the sample number possesses two main qualifications to participate in the self-administered survey. First, the sample member should be using promotional tools for buying purposes. Second, they never buy any item if there is any condition imposed on it.

We select these sample members from different metropolitan cities of Pakistan. Two main clusters will target to collect the sample data like university students and some of working professionals and businesspersons. The selection of students and working professionals based on previous results of the studies on purchase intention in case of sales promotional tools. According to Wood 2002, young adults are more interested in shopping in case of some discount and free sample as compared to others.

3.2. Instrument and measure

The survey instrument of the current study address two major purposes:

First is to analyze the relationship of different variables in the adoption of sale promotional tools. Second, to collect information about the different characteristics of the respondents that can b used to understand the variations in different categories.

The survey instrument contains two sections:

Section 1 includes different personal and demographic variables. This section will obtain the respondent’s information about gender, age, income, education and status.

Section 2 includes the latent variables that are important in the current study. These variables include attitude towards price

discount, attitude towards free sample, in-store display and purchase intention. This section of the study, which is developed, based on the past literature and already used questionnaires (Table 1).

The scales of the study, which we adopt is from the previous literature and published studies. The first two variables of the study are attitude towards price discount and attitude towards free sample. Each variable has eight items and the scales we take from Syuhaily Osman. Other variable is in-store display having four items was taken from Yalcin & Kocamaz, 2003. The last variable is purchase intention with seven factors and its scale we take from Pery et al. 2001.

Scales of Study:

No.	Variables	Items	Reference
1	Attitude towards Price Discount	If a brand, offers price discount that could be a reason for me to buy it. When I buy a brand that offers price discount, I feel I am getting a good buy. A price discount has allowed me to buy another brand, which I do not regularly buy. I usually buy the same brand even when I have a price discount on the other brands. I have favorite brands, but most of the time I buy a brand that offers price discount. A price discount has allowed me to buy the product earlier than planned. A price discount has allowed me to buy more quantities of the same product. Compared to most people, I am more likely to buy brands that offer price discount.	Syuhaily Osman

2	Attitude towards Free Sample	If brands offers free sample that could be a reason for me to buy it.	Syuhaily Osman
		When I buy a brand that offers free sample, I feel I am getting a good buy.	
		A free sample has allowed me to buy another brand, which I do not regularly buy.	
		I usually buy the same brand even when I have a free sample on the other brands.	
		I have favorite brands, but most of the time I buy a brand that offers free sample.	
		A free sample has allowed me to buy the product earlier than planned.	
		A free sample has allowed me to buy more quantities of the same product.	
3	In-Store Display	I buy such products even in case of no need when display attracts me.	Yalcin & Kocamaz
		I buy more quantity by seeing atmosphere of store and display.	
		I buy such kinds of goods, which have low quality by seeing attractive display.	
		I buy usually superior quality products at high prices when I see beautiful display.	
		Once I find a product I like, I buy it regularly.	
		In general, I try to get the best overall quality.	

4	Purchase Intention	I usually buy well-known brands.	Pery
		I prefer buy the best selling brands.	
		It is funny to buy something new and exciting.	
		I usually buy the lower price products.	
		I buy as much as possible at sale prices.	

3.3. Procedure

The questionnaire we distributed among 200 respondents in Rahim Yar Khan, Bahawalnagar and Bahawalpur. These respondents, whom we select, based on the criteria above mentioned. Before giving the questionnaire, the purpose of study and questions we explained to the respondents so they can easily fill the questionnaire with relevant responses. Total 150 questionnaires we select and rest of the questionnaires was not included in the further analysis due to incomplete or invalid responses. After collecting the completed questionnaires, these coded and entered into SPSS sheet for regression analysis.

3.4. Reliability analyses

Overall Cranach's alphas of all variables in our study are more than acceptable and recommended value 0.50 by Nunnally (1970) and 0.60 by Moss et al. (1998). This shows that all the 27 items were reliable and valid to measure the purchase intention of consumers towards sales promotional tools.

Table 2: Reliability of Measurement Instrument

Scale	Items	Cranach Alpha
Attitude towards Price Discount	8	0.518
Attitude towards Free Sample	8	0.681
In-Store Display	4	0.513
Purchase Intention	7	0.567

4. Results and Analysis

4.1 profile of the respondents

Personal and demographic information such as gender, age, income, education level and status given in the following table:

Table 3: Profile of the Respondents

	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Variable			
Gender	Male	105	70
	Female	45	30
Age	15-20 Years	51	34
	20-25 Years	93	62
	25-30 Years	3	2
	30-35 Years	2	1.3
	35-40 Years	1	0.7
	Above 40 Years	0	0
Income (Rs./Month)	Below 15000	98	65.3
	15000-25000	28	18.7
	25000-35000	6	4
	35000-45000	5	3.3
	45000-55000	2	1.3
	Above 55000	11	7.3
Education	Matriculation	16	10.7
	Intermediate	75	51.3
	Bachelor	50	33.3
	Master	7	4.7
	MS/M. Phil	0	0
	PhD.	0	0
Status	Student	142	94.7
	Employed	5	3.3
	Businessman	3	2
	Unemployed	0	0
	Housewife	0	0

4.3. Hypotheses testing

4.3.1 Attitude towards Price Discount

According to the results of the study, this variable has a positive relationship with purchase intention. Specifically, attitude towards price discount has a significant positive relationship with ($\beta=0.239$) and ($p < 0.01$). That means

attitude towards price discount contribute more than 25% to purchase intention. Result of the current study validates H1.

4.3.2 Attitude towards Free Sample :

According to the results of the study, this variable has a positive relationship with purchase intention. Specifically,

attitude towards free sample has a significant positive relationship with ($\beta=0.193$) and ($p < 0.05$). That means attitude towards free sample contribute more than 16% to purchase intention. Result of the current study validates H2.

4.3.3 In-Store Display

According to the results of the study, this variable has a negative relationship with purchase intention. Because, in-store display has a significant negative relationship with ($\beta=0.115$) and ($p > 0.05$). Based on these results, we reject H3.

Table 4: Regression Result

Hypotheses	Model Variable	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Results
H1	PIN ← ATPD	0.252	0.095	2.658	0.009	Supported
H2	PIN ← ATFS	0.164	0.077	2.125	0.035	Supported
H3	PIN ← ISD	0.084	0.060	1.413	0.160	Not Supported

Figure 2: Structural Model Results

5. Discussion

As we have learned through amount of existing studies at current substance, customer purchase intention is haziness for marketers and retailers, and a large amount leftover to learn about it. Numerous studies have tried to drop light on how customers make plans and build up the processes of buying. In many studies, the focus is on the process of brand choice. The study shows, this process contain on a series of related variables. Intention is different from customer to customer;

some factors influence one customer in one-way and different to another.

Like this, we can say that in purchase the price of products and brands formulate a variable of interest which provide help the customer to favor the purchasing or option of a particular brand (low price brand), or condense the likelihood of its purchasing or option (high price brand). Price of products are very important due to this importance consumers usually form a reference price. Hence, when the consumer is going to make decision to purchase a product she or he would make it

subsequent to comparing the price on offer with the reference price.

The consumer's choice for a product or brand affect by sales promotions. This is a fact that retailers to get solid objectives use sale promotion techniques. This fact is outstanding in measure. Before taking a decision, the consumer will take into consideration is there a promotion exists or not.

Promotions may also have a side effect because consumer is purchasing a product, which he usually does not purchase. Moreover, sales promotion can help the consumer to decide which brand he purchase when two different brands are equally striking to the consumer. Sales promotion is very important and productive technique, which help manufacturers and retailers in the accomplishment of their purposes.

In practice a wide range of sales promotion, techniques are used. Mostly, promotions in which there are direct price reductions are used. It proves that these techniques have a greater influence on the brand choice process, i.e. sales promotion positively influences the brand choice process.

Expressly, all the techniques that are in use, instant price discounts have greater effect on consumer purchase intention.

In practice, we should apply those promotional tools that give us better results. Taking into account the results, it looks that price-based promotions are more effective. This fact is very important, as some manufacturers and retailers can invest in such promotional activities that have no value by consumers.

It may be possible that the consumer perceives a promotion, for example discount or rebates, but it does not change his or her intention. In this situation, the manufacturers and retailers are investing their resources in promotions that do not have any effect on the consumer. It is very important for retailers and marketers to know the consumer's preferences and the dealings that greatly influence consumer-purchase intention. Hence, marketers should invest their resources in sales price.

As a result, consumer must take action after comparing the price on offer with the reference price.

However, different consumers have different preferences, they response different promotions differently. The marketer

should segment the market by distinguishing customers who are honest and loyal to a brand and who are not honest and loyal to a brand. It is necessary to take into consideration such different behaviors. Different types of strategies needed for these diverse segments. Strategies must be related these segments.

The variables we have used in our study are the most widely studied variables. However, it is necessary to take into account other variables. Thus, in the present paper, apart from considering the effect of the variables by now investigated, we have shown evidence of how sales promotion techniques influence the consumer's purchase and brand choice intention. In this way, we have made it clear there is a need to consider the product promotional state, purchase as a descriptive part of the process. As we have seen, models that include promotions possess have a greater descriptive capacity than those that do not.

Now there is a need to expend our work to other categories of product due to which choice of brand differ in customer to customer. It is very interesting to know that consumers' characteristics also have an influence on their responses to sales promotions (spending, faithfulness, socio-economic or demographic factors *etc*).

Therefore, we should expand the present work to other categories of product in which consumers show other preferences. It should possible to analyze categories of product that not bought with the same rate. It is also important we should judge those products for which consumer have strong brand preferences. It may be possible we judge that there are varieties of products whose buyers are reliable may favor another type of sale promotion technique. In this way, discounts that are the reward of the trustworthiness may have a larger upshot as compared to price cuts.

In addition, the uniqueness of customers also has an important place. How the response of households to sales promotion activities, varies according to the level of utilization of the product category, can analyzed. Promotional behavior varies

depending on the type of consumer (trustworthy or not trustworthy to a brand). The results show that trustworthy customers are sensitive to promotions.

We conclude that the structure gives some new approaching to understand that how IUB students act in response to a variety of promotional tools presented by market managers and the effects on the purchase intention, which might be fundamental for market managers in developing perfect marketing strategies to encourage brands and products.

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